

CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D27: CODECO Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme intermediate version

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Executive Summary

CODECO Deliverable D27 - "Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme Intermediate version" describes the plan of the CODECO engagement programme IRCEP. IRCEP is designed to foster collaboration and innovation among SMEs, academia/research, and early developers of diverse tools that fit within CODECO's target areas. By targeting these diverse groups, the program aims to cultivate a dynamic and inclusive ecosystem where varied talents and perspectives converge to drive the expansion of CODECO's ecosystem.

Stakeholders express their interest through a structured application process, which includes submission of forms, evaluation, and prompt communication of results. This streamlined approach ensures efficient participation and alignment with the program's objectives.

Detailed reporting mechanisms track program costs and event evaluations, ensuring transparency, accountability, and continuous improvement. These reports enable informed decision-making and optimization of IRCEP's impact on the CODECO ecosystem.

In addition to programmatic activities, IRCEP prioritizes Data Preservation, Storage, and Privacy. Robust measures are implemented to safeguard data integrity, confidentiality, and accessibility, ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements and stakeholder expectations. Furthermore, ethical considerations are central to IRCEP's framework. Ethical principles guide program design, implementation, and evaluation, ensuring that activities are conducted with integrity, respect for individuals' rights, and consideration of potential societal impacts.

The project's steadfast commitment to collaboration, innovation, and inclusivity drives the success of IRCEP in unlocking the full potential of the CODECO ecosystem.

Keywords: community engagement; outreach; dissemination.

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Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Meaning
ACM	Automated Configuration Management
AI	Artificial intelligence
AR	Academia and Research
CA	Consortium Agreement
CODECO	Cognitive Decentralized Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CRDs	Custom Resource Definitions
DEV	Developers
EC	European commission
ECO	Edge to Cloud
ETC	Ethics Committee
EU	European Union
EUs	End-Users
FOR	fortiss
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679
GOV	Government, municipalities, public authorities, and policymakers
HE	Horizon Europe
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
INO	Inova +
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
IRCEP	Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme
ISCC	International Symposium on Computers and Communications
K8s	Kubernetes
MDM	Metadata Management
Mx	Month x of the CODECO project
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
OCM	Open Cluster Management
OS	Open Source
OSS	Open-Source Software
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralized Learning and Context-awareness
SDO	Standardization entities and open-source communities
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SWM	Scheduling and Workload Migration

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1 Introduction

D27 serves as a comprehensive intermediate report on the contents of the CODECO *Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme (IRCEP)*, aiming to provide clarity and guidance on its practical applications. D27 is a deliverable developed in the context of WP7, Task 7.2 which started in April 2024 (M16) and shall continue until the end of the project (M36). D27 therefore describes the IRCEP plan, and presents initial steps taken in the first two months of its development.

D27 begins by exploring the theoretical underpinnings of the concept, shifting then to the multiple variables that directly result from said concept and form the bulk of the application process.

Reporting activities are then emphasized as crucial for collecting, analysing, and presenting essential data regarding this programme, with a focus on clear and transparent communication. The handling of data is then highlighted via strategies for preserving data integrity, secure storage practices. Moreover, mechanisms for safeguarding privacy are explored, guided by compliance with relevant regulations and ethical principles.

Lastly, ethical considerations are woven throughout the document, acknowledging their importance at every stage of the programme. The ethical implications of data collection, analysis, and dissemination are critically examined, with an emphasis on responsible use, transparency, and mitigating potential harms.

1.1 Document Structure

The deliverable is organized as follows:

- **Section 1**, where the document's introduction and structure are elaborated upon.
- **Section 2** is dedicated to the IRCEP concept.
- **Section 3** provides the definition of how IRCEP is applied, namely, its processes, timeline, evaluation methods, and expected results.
- **Section 4** covers the reporting in IRCEP.
- **Section 5** covers the processes for data preservation, storage, and privacy.
- **Section 6** describes ethical procedures.
- **Section 7** summarizes the deliverable.

1.2 Goals

Access to innovation by empowering communities with the skills, resources, and knowledge needed to participate actively in the research and development process is at the basis of IRCEP. This can involve events and conferences, innovation workshops, hackathon, summer schools and other collaborative initiatives that equip community members with a deeper understanding of scientific and technological processes. By fostering a culture of inclusive innovation, IRCEP encourages a broader base of stakeholders to engage in the creation and dissemination of new knowledge, thus promoting equity in the benefits derived from research and technological advancements.

Specifically, IRCEP's goal to create a mechanism via which diverse stakeholders can enter CODECO's ecosystem by building applications, services, and extensions of its framework. These diverse stakeholders are namely SMEs, early developers, researchers, and students in areas in close scientific proximity to the project's main action areas.

2 Concept

2.1 What is IRCEP?

The aim of IRCEP, supported by the pillars in Figure 1, is to further exploit the CODECO ecosystem by targeting the CODECO stakeholder groups. To do so, a series of activities will be made available to interested parties, with their evaluation being carried out under the following principles: (i) creativity and innovation; (ii) transparency; (iii) fairness and impartiality; (iv) confidentiality and ethics; (v) timely implementation and concrete deadlines.

Figure 1: IRCEP Pillars

Activities made available by IRCEP will be tailored towards specific target groups, which should, ideally, be closely connected to the 4 categories of use-cases across the domains of Smart Cities, Manufacturing, Energy and Smart Buildings, but also allow for external elements to propose extensions and experimentation across other domains. These specific groups, as displayed by Figure 2, can then be summarized into the below typologies: (i) Small and Medium Enterprises; (ii) Early Developers; (iii) Researchers and (iv) Students in relevant areas.

Figure 2: CODECO IRCEP Target Groups

Prospective participants always need to fit within the preceding target groups, but this is not the only criterion at hand. In tandem with the target groups categorization, they need to have demonstrable expertise in each event's field, their activities must generate co-relations with CODECO, and their motivation needs to be sufficiently elaborated upon and, essentially, they should align with CODECO's end goals.

2.2 Opportunities

CODECO's IRCEP calendar, available via a specific page on the CODECO Website¹, is being continuously updated to ensure that most relevant events within the project's key areas are tracked and open to the participation of the identified target groups. These events can fit into the following categories: (i) Events and Conferences; (ii) Innovation Workshops; (iii) Hackathons and (iv) Summer Schools.

Once a specific event is identified by INO (with suggestions being expected as well by all project partners) and approved by the project coordinator FOR, to be part of CODECO's IRCEP programme, then it will be officially announced on the project's website and social media channels. This announcement will disclose key components regarding each individual opportunity such as:

- Target areas.
- Location and date.
- Budget.
- Timeline.
- Full programme.
- Submission.

2.3 Opening

Considering the agreement established during CODECO's Grant Agreement discussions, IRCEP was initially presented in February 2024 with its official announcement and the first events have been published during the latter half of April 2024.

The first event supported by CODECO's IRCEP programme was the scientific workshop Edge to Cloud (ECO) 2024, with a conditional target of 2 to 3 papers being shortlisted by the project coordinator, FOR, and ATH. ECO 2024 will take place in Paris, France on June 26th, 2024, and is the 1st International Workshop on Edge to Cloud Orchestration, co-located with the 29th IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC).

3 Application

Stakeholders follow an application process to take part in an event supported by CODECO's IRCEP Programme. This process, mapped out in Figure 3, will allow the evaluation committee to receive all the necessary information for a successful assessment of all applications.

¹ <https://he-codeco.eu/ircep/>

It must be noted that in some specific scenarios, an application process might not apply, and selections are carried out according to external variables (e.g., selection of papers received by the event/workshop organizer and assessment carried out also by those parties).

Figure 3: CODECO IRCEP Application Process.

3.1 Forms

Prospective applicants will need to fill in a single form displayed in Figure 4, in line with the objective of making IRCEP applications as streamlined as possible. To do so, the application form will include the following elements:

- **Application norms**, in which general remarks about the application are given. These general remarks will, often, be about the website where registration is done, maximum amount that is supported regarding registration and when costs will be reimbursed.
- **Travel and Accommodation norms**, in which the way these costs need to be reported, are stated along with the maximum amount that will be reimbursed.
- **Section A:** General Information, section where each applicant's identification details are inserted.
- **Section B:** Specific Information, where the bulk of the information that will allow the assessment of applications will be provided. Specifically, applicants will elaborate upon their expertise in the opportunity's field, their co-relationship with CODECO and motivation to take part in the event/workshop. Applicants will also need to attach a copy of their Curriculum Vitae (even if they are part of a SME, university or other organizations disclosed as target groups under IRCEP).

CODECO IRCEP Applications

Disclaimer ✕

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General Information

Contact Name

Figure 4: CODECO IRCEP Application Form.

3.2 Timeline

Applications for events made available under the CODECO's IRCEP programme will be, generally, open for fifteen days. Following this period, two to three days will then be dedicated to the evaluation of the received forms with the results being communicated approximately five days after the closure of the submission period. A timeline of the entire process is presented in Table 1. Notwithstanding, the entire process should, ideally, be finalized one month prior to the specific event's start date.

Table 1: IRCEP Applications' Timeline.

Step	Description
Monitoring and publication of opportunities on CODECO's website	Monitoring of opportunities is done, tentatively, at a weekly basis.
Communication to evaluators	The most suitable evaluators, within the project, should be notified regarding each identified opportunity to gauge their availability to proceed with evaluations.
Application period	Once an opportunity is identified and duly published, applications will be open for a period of 15 days and applicants need to fill out the form displayed on Figure 5.
Evaluation period	The allocated evaluators, following the application step, should then proceed with the evaluation of applications. This process should take between two (2) to three (3) days.
Communication of results	Results should be announced five (5) days after the application period closes. Successful applicants are then contacted.
Follow-up	Once contacted, and to receive the reimbursement, participants need to provide two documents: (i) Participation report and (ii) Expenses report.

3.3 Evaluation

Evaluation of received applications will essentially focus on the three questions prospective applicants need to answer on Section B of the form. Each section will have a maximum grade of 5, towards a total possible maximum grade of 15.

Three evaluators will be needed for each opportunity that is made available. FOR, as the project coordinator and INO, as the leader of the IRCEP programme always need to be part of the evaluation team. The third member will vary according to the CODECO partner that is most involved in the respective event supported by IRCEP.

3.4 Results

Results will be announced at least one month prior to the selected event's start date. Selected applicants will be informed via the email they listed in Section A of the application form.

4 Reporting

4.1 Costs

For the selected applicants to be reimbursed the costs associated with IRCEP-supported events, they need to prepare a report where they list all the expenses that were incurred while taking part in the event. This report should be provided via an excel file and structured following the content guidelines below:

- Name of participant and event.
- Date and location of event.
- Date, type and amount of expense.
- Total amount of expenses.

Up to 2800 euros per person

PARTICIPATION PACKAGE

2 to 3

SELECTED APPLICATIONS

Figure 5: CODECO IRCEP Costs Support.

It is essential to note that expenses will only be reimbursed if receipts are duly attached when delivering the excel report and only if they fall within the limit of 2800 euros per selected person, as displayed on Figure 5.

This report should be delivered to the INO's team, and the file should be named "**CostsReport_CODECOIRCEP_[EventName]_[ParticipantName]**".

4.2 Event

In tandem with the necessary expense report, participants will also need to provide an attendance report in Microsoft Word format. This report needs to contain a thorough assessment of the participant's experience at the event and as such include the following sections:

- Section A: General Information regarding the event (Name, location, days attended).
- Section B: Evaluation (Sessions, event organization, project articulation).
- Section C: Summary (Closing remarks on their experience, gathering all components).

This report should be delivered to INO's team via the contact provided on the Website, and the file should be named "**CODECOIRCEP_[EventName]_[ParticipantName]**".

5 Data Preservation, Storage and Privacy

5.1 Data Storage and Backup

All data gathered during each application process will be stored and controlled by the CODECO Coordinator (FOR) and the INO team (CODECO management team). This data will be stored according to the conditions set out under the project's official Data Management Plan (CODECO D21).

5.2 Data Selection and Preservation

Data inserted and shared by applicants will only be used for the purpose of analysing the received forms and proceeding with the evaluation procedure as well as being stored and preserved for reporting purposes directly connected to CODECO. Moreover, only the data needed to carry out the defined purpose will be utilized and only for the strictly needed period for such.

5.3 Data Destruction

The different levels of data in CODECO are expected to live after the project lifetime. However, there may be cases where data expires, or one of the Partners (or external participants in the data collection) requests deletion of the data in accordance with Article 17 of the *General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR)*, which concerns the Right to erasure. In this case, the data responsible entity (rf. to Table 3) will handle a secure deletion process, after consultation with the CODECO Data Manager (INO) and the CODECO Coordinator (FOR). For this process, CODECO shall consider secure data erasure methods (e.g., specific software), ensuring that the deleted data will not be recoverable after destruction. Moreover, CODECO shall create an auditable report for the process.

6 Ethics

Ethical aspects in CODECO are handled in WP1. The data that will be collected during the CODECO project will be handled in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles. The CODECO data is under no specific legal requirements and will be shared after an embargo period, if applicable. No dataset containing confidential information, or any ethical or legal issues, will be deposited.

Particularly important is the CODECO third level of data, that might contain video and photography data of people. This needs to be anonymised as early as possible – preferably

on the edge directly – and blur out faces and license plates. Only then can the researchers continue to process this data and make it available to external persons following FAIR principles.

Additionally, the CODECO internal Ethics Committee (ETC) exists to support the analysis of the proposed activities regarding data management and ethics assessment support. The procedure for reporting by the ETC is detailed in CODECO deliverable D1 - Handbook and Gender-Neutral Guidelines being summarized here for the sake of clarity. The ETC will continuously communicate with the CODECO Executive Board (rf. To D1), and report to the GeA findings on each plenary meeting, and on extraordinary meetings, if required. The ETC shall meet regularly with the project management team and consortium, every quartal, aligned with the plenary meetings, to oversee the right approach to the handling of the project related data. This is further described in D1. The ETC will follow the proposed DME and ensure that partners follow the proposed rules, making sure that they conform to the legislation regulations in force in the countries where the research will be carried out, as well as to the EC Ethical Legislation.

6.1 Code of Conduct

The Code of Conduct for IRCEP establishes guidelines to ensure ethical, respectful, and productive collaboration among all participants. Core principles include respect, integrity, and inclusivity. Participants must respect diverse perspectives, backgrounds, and expertise, fostering an environment where every voice is valued. Integrity is crucial, requiring participants to adhere to honest and transparent practices in their research, reporting, and interactions. Inclusivity mandates the active engagement of all community members, ensuring that the benefits and burdens of innovation and research are equitably shared. Confidentiality is also emphasized, with participants expected to protect sensitive information and intellectual property, respecting the privacy and contributions of all parties involved.

Furthermore, the Code encourages the dissemination of findings in accessible formats, promoting broad understanding and the potential for real-world application.

6.2 GDPR Compliance

The consortium is committed to conducting the project in accordance with any applicable local laws that apply such as GDPR (collectively referred to as the EU Data Protection Legislation).

To ensure GDPR compliance, no data will be collected or used without the explicit informed consent of the subjects (e.g., users) concerned. In this direction, users/subjects provided data must sign a proper informed consent form. The form will make explicit for what purpose data is collected, who has access to the collected data, as well as for how long the data will be securely stored and subsequently deleted. Users/subjects will be also free to access their own data whenever they like. This will empower the Individuals involved to make a voluntary informed decision about whether to participate in CODECO processes based on knowledge of the scope, purpose, procedures, and outcomes of the project. Moreover, CODECO actors (e.g., end-users) will also have the possibility to gain access to additional information about their personal data and the way they are processed. Likewise, they will be able to revoke their consent at any time.

7 Summary and Next Steps

This interim report outlines the progress of the CODECO Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme. This programme aims to promote innovation among SMEs, academia/research, and early developers. Through a streamlined application process and robust reporting mechanisms, the IRCEP ensures efficient participation and transparency in its activities. Additionally, the program prioritizes Data Preservation, Storage, and Privacy, along with ethical considerations, to uphold integrity and respect for stakeholders. By adhering to these principles, the IRCEP continues to drive meaningful outcomes and unlock the full potential of the CODECO ecosystem.

References

- [1] Ana Solange (Ed.). D2 – Data Management and Ethics Handling v1.0, March 2023.
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